

STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES USING EMBEDDED WIRE SENSORS

P. Mertiny*, M. Ocker, C. Hansen, C. Ayranci

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada

* Corresponding author (pmertiny@ualberta.ca)

Keywords: *Structural health monitoring, Embedded sensors, Metal wire/filament*

1 Introduction

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRPC) are attractive materials for various industrial applications due to their high specific material properties and excellent resistance to environmental degradation such as corrosion. Often neglected in this context is the ability and comparative ease of embedding structural health monitoring (SHM) systems into a composite structure. The objectives for incorporating SHM systems are to assess the evolution of damage, detect critical damage states before failure, and enable preventive maintenance planning. These capabilities constitute additional operational advantages, and as such, cost savings may be realized compared to conventional metallic components. The present contribution reviews and reports on low-cost SHM systems for FRPC components based on embedded metallic wires/filaments, which henceforth will be termed fibrous sensor (FS). This study focusses on filament-wound parts, i.e. FRPC piping. Nevertheless, SHM techniques described herein are applicable to other FRPC manufacturing processes as well.

2 Wire-based SHM Systems

The physical effects exploited in the present context are principally electro-mechanical in nature. The arguably most straightforward approach employs the change in electrical resistance with applied deformation of an embedded FS, which is the subject matter of Section 2.1. This and similar techniques can be classified as SHM by strain measurement. The so-called magnetic wire sensor technique that is briefly described in Section 2.2 can be placed into this same category.

Both of the aforementioned techniques require a connection to both ends of the FS, which usually brings about added manufacturing complexity. Moreover, even though an embedded FS is well protected within the composite structure, its connections to power supply and data acquisition

equipment are exposed and are therefore vulnerable to external damage during transport, installation and operation of the FRPC component. In response to these challenges, techniques employing high-frequency electrical signal induction were examined as described in Section 2.3. Finally, electrical time-domain reflectometry (eTDR) was considered herein as another attractive method requiring only a single point of electrical connection to the FS (Section 2.4).

2.1 Electrical Resistance Change

The so-called Long-Gage-Strain sensor for concrete structure instrumentation described by Ayranci et al. [1] served as a model for a FS based on electrical resistance change. In a study by Mertiny et al. [2] a high-resistivity metal filament (Co55/Ni45 annealed constantan wire with 150 μm diameter (34.5 AWG) and polyimide insulation) was embedded during the filament winding manufacturing process of FRPC (basalt-fiber/epoxy) piping with a $\pm 60^\circ$ fiber architecture. One of the studied sensor orientations was a helical path along the reinforcement direction. The suitability of this sensor arrangement for SHM in FRPC piping was demonstrated by subjecting pipe specimens to biaxial loading conditions (see [3] for information on experimental techniques). Using data acquired from conventional strain gauge (SG) instrumentation for comparison, the experiments showed that strain values can be obtained with good accuracy from FS electrical resistance measurements and knowing the FS gauge factor defined by Eq.(1).

$$G = \frac{dR/R}{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where G , R and ε are the gauge factor, electrical resistance and wire strain respectively.

Note that the wire yield strain of 3760 μstrain was approximately half of the fiber strain that was usually recorded at specimen failure. Hence, plastic deformation of the FS needs to be considered for this

SHM application. When strains exceed the elastic range of the sensor, gauge factor data calibrated for plastic deformation may be used. This was previously shown in [1]. Plastic deformation increases the gauge factor for the plastic region compared to the elastic region due to an increased dislocation density in the material that affects electron movement. In the present study, the gauge factor for the range of elastic wire deformation was experimentally determined as 1.85, which increased to 2.01 upon exceeding the yield strength of the wire. Notably, strain measurements from the FS still agreed reasonably well with SG data even when plastic strains were present in the sensor (see Figure 1). It should be noted that readings from the FS are not subject to misleading readings brought about by localized damage effects in the composite structure. SGs often fail or give erroneous measurements due to elevated strain levels caused by localized composite matrix damage. In contrast, FS were able to provide measurements up to the ultimate failure of composite structures. Furthermore, suitably embedded FS allow for the detection of pipe damage and even excessive internal wear of a piping structure by indicating the loss of electrical conductance due to sensor severance (see Section 2.4 for additional design considerations regarding this sensing concept). SGs, on the other hand, can practically only be surface mounted and are limited to point measurements, requiring a SG network with complex wired or wireless data acquisition and transmission (DAQ) equipment in order to monitor large FRPC structures. Reduced system robustness and reliability are the likely outcome, which can be improved upon using an embedded FS measurement system.

Fig.1. Strain data from strain gauge and fibrous sensor electrical resistance measurements.

2.2 Magnetic Wire Sensor

An interesting yet seldom utilized technology in the form of a magnetic wire strain sensor was proposed in [4]. This technology is based on magnetoelastic properties of a film deposited on a copper wire. The impedance of this very specific (and thus not widely available) wire is dominated by the film which is highly sensitive to strain. Due to small thickness and axisymmetry the magnetic coating is easily driven into saturation creating a magnetic field around the wire by modest alternating currents. A complex current/voltage relationship must be expected, which is influenced by the amplitude of the drive current and its frequency. An excitation current with appropriate frequency and amplitude produces spikes in the output waveform that change significantly with the applied strain, i.e. a decreasing spike amplitude is indicative of increasing strain. The output signal can further be converted to a DC voltage using a high-pass filter and rectifier. By application of multiple magnetic coating sections a localized assessment of large structures is possible (see schematic in Figure 2). However, such a concept requires multiple connections for data acquisition and transmission, which poses challenges associated with complex manufacturing and operational robustness and reliability.

Fig.2. Schematic of linear sensor array produced by multiple depositions of magnetic material coating; adapted from [4].

2.3 Electromagnetic Signal Induction

It was shown in [2] that an embedded FS may act as a solenoid allowing for the induction of an alternating electrical signal using external excitation and sensing coils. The concept is depicted by the schematic and picture shown in Figures 3 and 4 respectively. This configuration was found capable of detecting component failure that is accompanied by the severance of the FS, e.g. excessive pipe wear. However, experiments revealed a complex sensor response to the high-frequency sinusoidal input that,

albeit being sensitive to strain, was challenging to evaluate. Consequently, electrical signal induction is considered less practical at this point, despite advantages of not requiring a direct/physical FS connection, and additional studies on this technology are required.

Fig.3. Schematic of electromagnetic field being induced in the secondary coil with changing current in the primary coil.

Fig.4. Demonstrator setup for study of inductive signal transmission effects.

2.4 Electrical Time-Domain Reflectometry

eTDR is a measurement technique in which reflections from an emitted electromagnetic pulse are assessed in the time domain to derive conclusions about the state of the medium through which the signal is transmitted. Referring to the schematic shown in Figure 5 the signal propagates through a medium with constant velocity v . When the signal reaches a fault in the medium, i.e. a change in impedance of the transmitter, the pulse is partially or completely reflected, and the reflected signal travels back to the source. Knowing the velocity of the propagating signal in the medium as well as the travel time it is possible to determine

how far the signal has traveled in the medium in total. The concept of eTDR has already been explored for use in polymer composite structures. Using a dual-wire transmission line, Dominauskas et al. [5] successfully demonstrated that the flow front in liquid composite molding can be identified in-situ with eTDR due to permittivity changes caused by the emanating resin. Similarly, AbuObaid et al. [6] used eTDR to accurately assess mode I crack propagation in double cantilever beam specimens.

Fig.5. Schematic of eTDR working principle.

To explore the suitability of eTDR for SHM in polymer-based piping an experimental setup with a dual-wire transmission line made from insulated copper filaments embedded in a helically path inside a polymer pipe was developed, built and tested successfully (see Figure 6). A two-wire transmission line consisting of two parallel wires was selected due to ease of availability and an electromagnetic field that, in contrast to a coaxial conductor arrangement, also propagates into the medium surrounding the transmission line (see schematic in Figure 7). The impedance for such a transmission line depends on the separation distance between the conductors, D , the wire diameter, d , the conductor material properties, and the dielectric properties of the surrounding medium. Consequently, measurements are sensitive to the dielectric constant of the surrounding material, considering the wire separation distance and properties to be constant. In other words, this transmission line arrangement is not only capable of detecting line damage (severed wire) due to total signal reflection, but also, to some extent, property changes of the surrounding medium.

For the experiments, ordinary wire conductors with a diameter of $160 \mu\text{m}$ (i.e. 34 AWD magnet wire) were chosen that featured polyurethane/Nylon insulation with thickness of $30 \mu\text{m}$. The conductor pair maintained constant center-to-center distance as they were placed into a V-shaped groove that was machined with a helix angle of 88° into a commercial acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) pipe with inside and outside diameter and length of 101.6 mm, 114.3 mm and 1613 mm respectively.

The emitted eTDR signal was an electric pulse with 30 ns width that was created using a Tektronix AFG 3022B function generator. Signals were captured by a Tektronix MSO 4054 oscilloscope with a bandwidth of 500MHz. A creel with ~100 m of 50 RG/58 coax cable was used to connect the dual-wire transmission line, i.e. the ‘device under test’ (DUT), to the oscilloscope and function generator via a custom connection (see Figure 8) and a standard T-connector on the emitter side. Note that a considerable length of coax cable was used to avoid any signal reflection within the so-called blind spot. A signal produced by an impulse generator occupies a certain time span to fully emanate into the transmission line. The distance the pulse advances into the transmission line until the signal is completely introduced is known as the blind spot. Within the blind spot it is difficult to locate reflection signals associated with line faults.

Fig.6. Schematic of helical dual-wire transmission line (red) placed into groove in plastic piping.

Fig.7. Two-wire transmission line schematic showing electric (red) and magnetic (blue) flux.

Fig.8. eTDR test specimen with coaxial connector.

The analytically calculated impedance for the given transmission line arrangement was $Z = 53.9 \Omega$. This value is close to 50Ω , which is the standard impedance for common eTDR equipment and cables, e.g. the coaxial cable utilized in this study. It should be mentioned that impedance matching is essential to minimize signal reflection and thus signal attenuation when the electrical pulse enters the DUT from and to the signal generation and detection equipment.

Testing showed that damage in the structure, being simulated by severing the transmission line, could be detected and located from the signal response with good accuracy. Evaluating the time domain responses shown in Figure 9 yields damage locations that were on average within 50 to 75 mm with respect to the total pipe length. Note that this evaluation considers the helical wire arrangement. Figure 9 also illustrates that the transmission line is subject to energy losses as indicated by peak amplitudes that diminish with signal travel time, i.e. distance. Despite these limitations the collected data demonstrates that an embedded sensor as shown in Figure 10 is capable of detecting damage in the form of cracking or excessive wear inside a polymer piping structure (e.g. a polymer liner).

The influence of water partially filling the pipe on the eTDR signal was investigated as well. A considerable effect on signal responses is conceivable since water has a relative permittivity of 80 at room temperature while values for air and most polymers are unity and less than 5 respectively. However, with the current test setup no influence of water filling the pipe on the eTDR response could be ascertained. This result was attributed to an electromagnetic field that did not sufficiently extend beyond the polymer material separating wire sensor and fluid. Future testing with locally reduced

polymer thicknesses is planned to further explore the capabilities of eTDR to monitor liner wear within piping structures as shown by the schematic in Figure 11. Also considered in this context is the effect on signal responses by polymers modified with electroactive filler materials such as graphene, which may considerably enhanced the relative permittivity of the polymer.

Figure 9. Time domain eTDR responses for open-end transmission line simulating a severed FS at (a) 14.2 m, (b) 32.0 m and (c) 45.2 m wire lengths.

Fig.10. Schematic of polymer-lined piping with embedded eTDR FS.

3 Conclusions

Research on wire/filament sensors embedded in polymer-based and composite piping structures as reviewed in this paper confirms that inexpensive yet capable structural health and wear monitoring systems can be developed using a range of suitable measurement principles. In particular, methods based on electrical resistance change and electrical time-domain reflectometry emerge as promising in this context, and future research and development efforts are considered advisable.

Fig.11. Schematic of partially worn polymer liner and exposed FS in piping structure.

References

- [1] C. Ayranci, A. Fahim and M. Munro "A novel strain sensor for reinforced concrete structures". *Strain*, Vol.44, No.2, pp. 191-200, 2008.
- [2] P. Mertiny, C. Hansen and J. Kotlarski "Structural health monitoring using embedded metal filaments in polymer composite piping". *Proceedings of ASME Pressure Vessels and Piping Division Conference*, Prague, Czech Republic, PVP2009-77983, 2009.
- [3] P. Mertiny, K. Juss and M.M. El Ghareeb "Evaluation of Glass and Basalt Fiber Reinforcements for Polymer Composite Pressure Piping". *Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology*, Vol.131, pp. 061407-1 061407-6, 2009.
- [4] W.J. Biter, S.M. Hess, S. Oh, A. Geshury and D. Heider "Magnetic Wire For Monitoring Strain In Composites". *Sensor Magazine*, Vol.6, pp. 110-114, 2001.
- [5] A. Dominauskas, D. Heider and J.W. Gillespie Jr. "Electric time-domain reflectometry distributed flow sensor". *Composites A*, Vol.38, No.1, pp. 138-146, 2007.
- [6] A. AbuObaid, S. Yarlagadda, M.K. Yoon, N.E. Hager III. and R.C. Domszy "A Time-domain Reflectometry Method for Automated Measurement of Crack Propagation in Composites during Mode I DCB Testing". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol.40, No. 22, pp. 2047-2066, 2006.